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An experimental study on the use of Rice Husk Ash in Recycled Coarse Aggregate Concrete as a replacement for Cement and Fine Aggregate

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to produce higher-strength recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) by using rice husk ash (RHA) as a partial replacement material for cement and fine aggregate (sand), respectively. And aimed to introduce RHA in concrete as a cementitious component, which can be used as a percent replacement of sand as a strength enhancement admixture or as a percent replacement of cement for economical purposes. The test was conducted in two series. In both series, the mix ratio was 1:1.5:3 (cement: fine aggregate: coarse aggregate) for grade M20 with a different water-cement (w/c) ratio. Samples were tested for workability, water absorption, and compressive strength. In the first series, the water-cement ratio varied for different conditions of the concrete mixture to obtain the same workability condition. Rice husk ash was replaced by 10% of the cement and fine aggregate, by weight, sequentially. Both samples with 10% rice husk ash as a replacement for cement and sand showed nearly the same compressive strength compared to each other after 28 days. The strength was compared with normal aggregate concrete (NAC), and with the recycled aggregate concrete (RAC) without rice husk ash introducing shows relatively smaller strength. So, for an economic purpose, cement replacement was more suitable than sand replacement with rice husk ash. But, recycled aggregate concrete doesn't gain strength by introducing RHA. So, RHA doesn't improve the concrete quality, but it can be used as a partial replacement of cement for economical purposes. In the second series, the compressive strength was also measured for the same water-cement ratio to determine the effect of water-cement ratio on concrete strength. Then it exhibits

that cement replacement with rice husk ash concrete results in more strength compared to sand replacement with rice husk ash concrete. But this time, RAC without RHA also shows

better performance than with RHA. So, RHA doesn't improve the concrete quality, but it can be used as a partial replacement of cement for economical purposes.

Keywords: *recycled coarse aggregate, natural coarse concrete, recycled aggregate concrete, normal aggregate concrete, rice husk ash*

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste has long been recognized as one of the most significant environmental concerns in the modern world. Researchers all around the world are constantly attempting to come up with innovative ways to reduce solid waste disposal. However, the contribution of large-scale building and disposal of structural waste has a significant impact on overall solid waste accumulation. The global amount of C&D (Construction and Demolition) debris generated in 2018 was estimated to be around 600 million tons. In almost all countries, the building industry makes a significant contribution to the generation of solid waste. Construction and demolition debris estimates 25–40% of total waste created in North America, depending on the region [1]. By recycling the tons of demolished concrete trash, the use of an enormous amount of natural resources can be scaled down. Recycling demolished concrete and transforming it into recycled concrete aggregate could be the most effective way to reduce the quantity of solid waste disposed of each year throughout the world. But the main problem of reusing the RCA in concrete is the reduction of strength. So, for the enhancement of strength purpose some cementitious by-product components can be mixed for strength augmentation purposes. The supplementary materials like fly ash, silica fume, Rice Husk Ash (RHA), metakaolin, etc., can be added in a designed quantity during cement production or during concrete production for strength enhancement purposes.

Rice husk ash waste also causes dangerous environmental problems in the soil and air. One way to reduce the environmental impact of rice husk ash is to process the waste and use it as a partial replacement for cement., which will reduce the amount of carbon dioxide (CO²) emitted annually in the atmosphere. In the modern world, countless studies are looking at using industrial or agricultural wastes as a source of raw materials for the construction sector. Rice milling produces a by-product called husk, which forms the outer covering of the paddy grain. During the milling process, approximately 78% of the total weight is obtained as rice and broken rice, while the remaining 22% is husk. This rice husk consists of nearly 75% organic volatile substances, and the remaining 25% is converted into ash when the husk is burned, producing rice husk ash (RHA). The resulting RHA contains about 85% to 90% amorphous silica. Therefore, for every 1000 kg of paddy processed, around 220 kg of husk is generated, and burning this husk in a boiler produces approximately 55 kg of rice husk ash. For the cheap and economical generation of concrete, rice husk is used as a partial replacement of cement. It also serves as an admixture in concrete to enhance the properties by replacing the sand. The quality and strength of concrete are basically related to its compressive strength. In addition to this, the concrete also gains strength and durability due to the pozzolanic properties of Rice Husk Ash [2]. The pozzolanic activity of RHA is influenced by the content of silica, silica crystallization

phase, and size and surface area of ash particles. In order to ensure the quality of ash, a suitable incinerator/furnace, as well as a grinding method, is required for burning and grinding. It is observed that RHA contains more than 75-80% silica, and it shows a lower loss on ignition [3].

Millions of tons of cement are consumed yearly for the construction of buildings, highways, etc. The production of cement requires a lot of energy, and it also generates harmful gases that affect the environment. The cement consumption can be decreased by including supplementary cementitious materials (like fly ash, silica fume, Rice Husk Ash, metakaolin, etc.) in concrete production and also in granular materials. Thus, the rice husk ash, if used in concrete production, can reduce numerous costs and environmental hazards [4]. However, by recycling the tons of demolished concrete trash, the use of an enormous amount of natural resources can be scaled down. And after combining both wastes (RCA & RHA) together can be a revolutionary idea by which RHA can overcome the strength reduction problem of RAC and could be the most effective way to recycle both wastes together.

OBJECTIVES

- To improve the strength and durability of recycled concrete aggregate (RCA) by introducing RHA.
- To evaluate the workability of fresh concrete with different w/c ratios.
- To determine the optimum mix proportion of RHA in concrete
- To investigate the better approach between cement and sand partial replacement with RHA.
- To invent more cost-effective, sustainable & eco-friendly construction.

LITERATURE SURVEY/REVIEW

An observation made by Waliuddin et al in 1996 by utilizing rice husk ash as a cement substitute in concrete with a percentage of

0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, and the addition of super plasticizer. According to this study, concrete containing 10% rice husk ash showed the highest average compressive strength, reaching 38.5 MPa after 7 days and 56.2 MPa after 28 days [5].

In 2024, Alwan et al investigated the key performance properties of high-strength, high-performance concrete. High-strength, high-performance concrete incorporating 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% rice husk ash. The 7 and 28 day curing periods, the compressive and flexural strengths of concrete containing 10 % of rice husk ash admixture were better compared to the control concrete that incorporate 5% and 15% of rice husk ash. The compressive strengths of 48.6 MPa at 7 days and 57.9 MPa at 28 days demonstrate the effectiveness of rice husk ash as an admixture for producing high-strength concrete [6].

An observation made by Kamaruddin et al that untreated rice husk ash was substituted for a portion of the volume of fine aggregate in concrete at a ratio of 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30% by volume of sand. The compressive strength was tested after 28 days for the experimental analysis, and a total of 12 specimens were tested. The findings of a hardened concrete test, similar to the compressive tests, demonstrate that rice husk ash may be successfully replaced at less than 10% by the weight of fine particles in concrete products [7].

In 2013, Yadav et al also found that the optimum replacement was 10% replacement of cement for compressive strength. The study conclude that rice husk ash is a good pozzolanic as it attains up-to 92.9% design strength at 28 days curing period, but increase the ingress of moisture into concrete, however, when used at 10%

partial replacement, the effect will not be of great concern [8].

Mohseni et al carried out a comprehensive study at 28 days for 0% Rice Husk Ash has the highest value, which is 12.89 N/mm² and 50% of Rice Husk Ash has the lowest value of 2.78 N/mm². This indicates that concrete containing a 10% replacement of rice husk ash is suitable for use in light load structural applications [9].

However, Amarachi et al also reported that the cement was partially replaced with rice husk and rice husk ash at proportions of 9.5%, 10.5%, and 11.5%, with 1% super plasticizer added to each mix. The concrete compressive strength tests were conducted at 14 and 28 days, targeting a normal concrete strength of 25 MPa. The results showed that the mix containing 9.5% rice husk ash and 1% superplasticizer produced the highest compressive strength, highlighting the potential of these by-products in sustainable concrete production [10].

According to Chao et al. (2022), the target compressive strength of the concrete was 45 MPa, with rice husk ash used as a cement replacement at levels of 5%, 10%, and 15% by weight. The study reported that at 7 days, the compressive strengths were 30.59 MPa, 25.20 MPa, and 20.77 MPa for 5%, 10%, and 15% replacement levels, respectively. At 14 days, the compressive strength increased to 37.48 MPa for 5%, 27.56 MPa for 10%, and 22.23 MPa for 15% replacement. The strength further improved at 28 days, reaching 44.26 MPa, 29.36 MPa, and 29.19 MPa for 5%, 10%, and 15% rice husk ash replacement, respectively [11].

Rashad et al. (2015) evaluated the use of rice husk ash as an admixture in concrete under normal environmental conditions by examining the effects of adding 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% rice husk ash to Grade 20

and Grade 30 concrete. The results indicated that the slump of concrete increased as the percentage of rice husk ash increased for both concrete grades. The compressive strength of water-cured concrete specimens improved with the addition of 5% and 10% rice husk ash; however, the 5% replacement level showed a more significant improvement in strength. When the rice husk ash content was increased to 15%, a reduction in compressive strength was observed [12].

Solikin et al (2016) determined that rice husk obtained from rice mills was incinerated and blended into powder form and introduced into self-compacting concrete mix as a partial substitute for cement in percentages of 0, 5, 10, 15, and 20. The compressive strength and mass of concrete samples exposed to acid attack in 56 and 90 days showed that the reduction in compressive strength masses of concrete containing 5% and 10% rice husk ash was less than that of the corresponding control samples, at 15% and 20%, the reductions were more than the control. Thus, the durability performance of concrete containing rice husk ash improved when cement replacement was limited to 10% compared with the control specimens [13].

Aegula et al observed that the (OPC) cement has been replaced by RHA accordingly in the range of 10% and 20% by weight of cement for 0.30, 0.35, and 0.40 water/cement ratios. The test results showed that replacing cement with rice husk ash up to 10% produced optimum compressive strength without negatively affecting the properties of fresh and hardened concrete [14].

Selvaraja et al (2017) made blocks with two types of rice husk ash: low-carbon content RHA (inner layer) and high-carbon content RHA (outer layer). Cement blocks were produced using rice husk ash as a partial cement replacement at levels of 5%,

10%, 15%, and 20%, incorporating both low-carbon and high-carbon rice husk ash. The results showed that cement blocks containing low-carbon rice husk ash exhibited slightly improved workability, mechanical strength, and durability compared to those made with high-carbon rice husk ash. Nevertheless, both types of rice husk ash cement blocks met the requirements specified by relevant standards. Although the use of high-carbon rice husk ash did not result in significant improvements in strength or durability, its application is still considered advantageous due to its economic and environmental benefits in cement block production [15].

In recent years, over the last few decades, using RA has become popular with the increase in shortage of NA sources and also the reduction of landfill areas. So, it would be more sustainable and suitable for reducing the expense and natural resource consumption by reusing the previous one after processing. Using RHA as an admixture with RCA can be more effective

by yielding a stronger concrete. The combination of RCA with RHA as a replacement for cement will also provide a more cost-effective, sustainable, and eco-friendly construction solution in the current world.

METHODOLOGY

Specimen Details

To establish the goal of this study, the experimental work was done in two series. In the first series, four batches of specimens were formed, and each batch built three cylindrical specimens whose dimensions were 100mm by 200mm. For the first two batches: NCA and RCA, the mix concrete w/c ratios were 0.46. For the other two batches: RCA with 10% RHA as a cement replacement and RCA with 10% RHA as a sand replacement, the w/c ratios were respectively 0.62 and 0.76. In the second series, the four batches of specimens were built with three specimens per batch. The w/c ratio was 0.78 and fixed for all three batches. The whole procedure was mentioned in (Table-1).

Table 1: Test Plan.

Series	Batch No.	Mix	W/C	Number of Specimens
First series	1	NCA Concrete	0.46	3
	2	RCA Concrete	0.46	3
	3	RCA + 10% RHA (Cement Replace) Concrete	0.62	3
	4	RCA + 10% RHA (Sand Replace) Concrete	0.78	3
Second series	1	RCA Concrete	0.78	3
	2	RCA + 10% RHA (Cement Replace) Concrete	0.78	3
	3.	RCA + 10% RHA (Sand Replace) Concrete	0.78	3

MATERIALS

Portland Composite Cement (PCC) is used as a binding material for all concrete mixes (Figure-1(a)) which unit weight of 1440 kg/m³ (General Unit Weight of Composite Cement). Brick chips were used as natural coarse aggregate for some specific mixes

of concrete. Crushed brick chips with a 1-inch downgrade in size were collected from local suppliers (Figure-1(b)). In this study, recycled aggregate was collected from a demolished structure (Figure-1(c)). It was taken from a 20-year-old concrete construction that had been dismantled. The

building's Structural Member-Slab part was the principal source of experimentally demolished concrete. The collected concrete pieces were crushed manually/mechanically to obtain coarse aggregates of approximately 1-inch downgrade size (Figure-1(d)). Locally available Sylhet sand was used as fine

aggregate (less than 5mm in size) (Figure 1(e)) which unit weight of 1440kg/m^3 (General value for River Sand). The rice husk was first collected from a rice mill and then made into rice husk ash by manual incineration in open air, which was used as a partial replacement of cement and sand (Figure-1(f)).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 1: Materials (a) Cement (b) Natural Coarse Aggregate (NCA) (c) Pile Cap (d) Recycled Coarse Aggregate (RCA) & (e) River Sand.

Aggregate Properties

The qualities and behavior of concrete are heavily influenced by aggregate properties. At the beginning of the research, some required aggregate tests were carried out to understand and explain the effect of RCA on the qualities and performance of concrete. Sieve Analysis and Fineness Modulus Tests on coarse aggregates (Both NCA+RCA) were performed following ASTM C136-96A standard method for coarse aggregates. Performing sieve

analysis will help to determine the particle size distribution of NCA and RCA, and can compare the consistency and similarity between them. In Figure 2, it can be shown that the coarse aggregate NCA and RCA distributions in each batch of concrete mix are roughly equivalent. However, both graphs demonstrate that NCA had a slightly higher finer percentage than RCA because aggregates are not broken down too finely when turning demolished concrete blocks into RCA.

Fig. 2: Comparison of particle size distribution between RCA & NCA.

The ASTM method C127-88 was used to test the specific gravity and water absorption of coarse aggregate. The ASTM C29/C 29M-97 was used to conduct bulk density (unit weight) tests on coarse aggregate. The physical properties of course were determined in Table-2. The significant parameter connected to the condition of how densely the aggregate particles are packed in a certain volume is the unit weight of aggregate. Furthermore, the actual unit weight of aggregate should be known to calculate the needed amount of each aggregate for each concrete mix. To establish RCA behavior, earlier investigations on RCA have found that the quality and quantity of attached old mortar influence the unit weight and water absorption capacity of RCA. Table-2 shows that the unit weight of RCA is less than the unit weight of NCA. This is

demonstrated by the fact that RCA obtained from demolition concrete had a lower density than RCA due to adhered old mortar. Due to the RCA collected from a 20-year-old building, the parent coarse aggregate was brick chips, whose unit weight and specific gravity were higher than the NCA or brick chips may be due to the higher density of parent concrete or due to going through of 20year long stress condition, it has become denser. As a natural consequence, the water absorption capacity of RCA is influenced by its unit weight, with a larger unit weight indicating lower water absorption capacity. Table 2 shows that the unit weight of the RCA is greater than the unit weight of the NCA, which explains the reason that RCA has a lower absorption capacity. Even though the NCA has a higher unit weight than the RCA, it has a higher water absorption

capacity due to higher porosity, which makes it more able to absorb water. The rice husk ash property was unable to be

determined due to a deficiency of a proper code reference.

Table 2: Physical Properties of Coarse Aggregate.

PROPERTIES	RCA	NCA
Unit weight (kg/m ³)	1109.42	1086.67
SSD Unit weight(kg/m ³)	1232.68	1338.32
Bulk Sp. Gr. (OD)	1.983	1.696
Bulk Sp. Gr. (SSD)	2.203	2.089
Apparent Sp. Gr.	2.543	2.794
Absorption (%)	11.11	23.158
% Voids	43.941	35.8

Sampling, Mixing, and Curing

To construct the specimens, 100 mm diameter and 200 mm length cylinder molds were used. For sampling and curing of the test specimen, ASTM C31/C31M-19 standard practice for making and curing concrete test specimens in the field was followed and demolded after one day of casting and curing was done in a water tank for 28 days. The mix ratio was 1:1.5:3 (Cement: FA: RCA),

which was determined according to the ACI concrete mix proportion, and the water-cement ratios differed for each batch. The w/c ratio was selected according to the preferred workability condition and also considering the better performance behavior of recycled aggregate with rice husk ash. The mixing and curing procedures are shown in figure-3(a) & (b).

Fig. 3: (a) Mixing & (b) Curing.

Compressive Strength Test

After 28 days of curing concrete specimens, the compressive strength of concrete was measured for all mixes of

both series tests by using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) under the ASTM C39/C39M-01 method, as shown in Figure 4.

(a) Before crushing, (b) After crushing.
Fig. 4: (a) Before crushing, (b) After crushing.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The results of the compressive strength of the specimens were provided in Table-3.

For different conditions of both series, each batch shows a significant value.

Table 3: Compressive strength results.

Series	Batch No.	Mix	Strength (MPa) 28 Days	W/C	Strength increase or decrease (%)
First series	1.	NCA mix	8.32	0.46	-
	2.	RCA mix	8.6	0.46	3.37
	3.	RCA + 10% RHA (Cement Replace)	6.17	0.62	-25.8
	4.	RCA + 10% RHA (Sand Replace)	6.17	0.78	-25.8
Second series	1.	RCA mix	10.238	0.78	-
	2.	RCA + 10% RHA (Cement Replace)	7.523	0.78	-26
	3.	RCA + 10% RHA (Sand Replace)	6.170	0.78	-39.7

From Figure 5, it has been observed in series-1 for different w/c ratios that the compressive strength of batch 2 concrete compared to batch 1 increased. That indicates the RCA properties were better than the NCA, which favors gaining more strength. So, for further investigation in batches 3 & 4, 10% RHA is introduced to achieve more strength. But it exhibits less strength compared to batch 2. That may be due to the RHA used in this research contains high

carbon, which conduce higher absorption capacity and retard the hydration reaction of concrete. Because high-carbon RHA bears low silica content and disrupts the pozzolanic reaction of concrete [15]. But when it comes to comparing batch 2 & 4 concrete, it indicates that both samples seem same strength. So, it's suitable to use RHA as a replacement for cement instead of as a replacement for fine aggregate.

Fig. 5: Compressive strength graph (series-1).

From Figure 6, the relationship between the three batches of concrete for the same water-cement ratio manifests that batch 1 gained the highest strength among the other two batches, which was similar to series 1. However, when it comes to comparing batch 2 & 3 data, that is, cement and sand replacement with RHA, respectively, then it shows that cement replacement has more strength than fine

aggregate replacement. Because the replacement was conducted by weight for both batch 2 & 3. That's why cement replacement by RHA affixes less carbon content than sand replacement. The high carbon content in concrete is the main reasoning of the reduction in strength [15]. So, compared to both phenomena, it is better to replace cement substances with sand.

Fig. 6: Compressive strength graph (series-2).

The results of the workability of the specimens were provided in Table-4 of both series for different w/c ratios. For

different conditions of both series, each batch shows a significant relationship.

Table 4: Slump value results.

Series	Batch No.	Mix	Workability (Slump in mm)
First series	1.	NCA mix	15
	2.	RCA mix	13
	3.	RCA + 10% RHA (Cement Replace)	10
	4.	RCA + 10% RHA (Sand Replace)	8
Second series	1.	RCA mix	13
	2.	RCA + 10% RHA (Cement Replace)	10
	3.	RCA + 10% RHA (Sand Replace)	8

From Figure 7, in series 1, the workability was nearly the same for all batches of concrete. Because during the casting period, the workability for all four batches

is attempted to keep similar and try to achieve an optimum mixture of concrete after introducing RHA [14].

Fig. 7: Workability value (series-1).

From Figure 8, in series 2, the workability is decreased after adding RHA because RHA absorbs much more water due to the presence of porous high-carbon particles [15]. The 10% cement replacement with RHA shows a higher slump value than

sand replacement. Because replacement occurs by weight, for that reason sand replacement absorbs more water compared to cement replacement and shows a lower slump value.

Fig. 8: Workability value (series-2).

From the above configuration, compressive strength doesn't increase after affixing RHA in concrete. This is because the rice husk ash was produced through open-air, low-temperature burning, which resulted in a high carbon content. High carbon doesn't help that much to gain concrete strength due to the lower silica content [15]. But in the case of selection between cement and sand replacement with RHA. In this case, cement replacement was more cost-effective and efficient in comparison to sand replacement.

CONCLUSION

The compressive strength of RCA can be enhanced by affixing cementitious material like RHA. But the making procedure must be conducted in control limited oxygen environment. Like in a closed furnace with a minimum 400⁰ °C, slow uniform temperature. In that way, carbon oxidizes and produces low carbon, which helps to produce higher-strength concrete. It also helps to produce high amorphous silica content, which helps in pozzolanic reaction and enhanced strength.

But in comparison between replacement cement and replacement, then it's more suitable to replace cement than sand, and also cost-effective. So, for both economic and efficient purposes, cement must be prioritized to replace sand.

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